

A Prospective Study Assessing Diffusion-Weighted Imaging Effects of Intravascular Contrast Agent on Apparent Diffusion Coefficient Measures of Ovarian Neoplasms

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Aim: The aim of the present study was to assess the Diffusion-weighted imaging effects of intravascular contrast agent on apparent diffusion coefficient measures of ovarian neoplasms.

Methods: This was a Prospective Study was conducted on 50 patients at department of Radiology, with Study population being women with newly diagnosed ovarian tumors who underwent CEMRI study to evaluate the nature of tumor and extent.

Results: Most of the patients belonged to >60 years of age. 30 were benign and 20 were malignant. Most of the patients had size of tumor from 101-200 mm. In benign ovarian tumors, Pre contrast mean ADC was 1.49 ± 0.47 and Post contrast mean ADC value was 1.42 ± 0.68 with statistically insignificant P value. In malignant ovarian tumors, Pre contrast mean ADC was 0.91 ± 0.20 and post contrast mean ADC value was 0.94 ± 0.23 with statistically insignificant P value.

Conclusion: ADC measures using our approach were not significantly changed after contrast administration for ovarian tumors at 1.5T. Our findings support the possibility that DWI optimized may be obtained before or after DCE-MRI without compromising important clinical information. Benign ovarian tumors had higher ADC values compared to malignant tumors, consistent with some of the previous studies.

Keywords: DCE-MRI, DWI, ADC, Ovarian tumors, pre and post contrast

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Introduction

Dynamic contrast-enhanced magnetic resonance imaging (DCE-MRI) is widely used to characterize and delineate the extent of breast malignancies. Malignancies are distinguishable on DCE-MRI due to alterations in microvasculature characteristics, and can be detected with high sensitivity. In a meta-analysis across 44 breast MRI studies, sensitivity ranged from 89 to 100% for invasive cancers. [1] However, specificity was more variable, ranging widely from 21% to 100%, with an overall specificity of 72%. [1] Diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI) is a non-contrast-enhanced MRI technique that has shown promise for improving upon the specificity of DCE-MRI. [2-4] DWI assesses molecular water motion in tissue and complements DCE-MRI because it is sensitive to tissue microstructural features, including cell density and membrane integrity. [5] Multiple studies have indicated that apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC)

values measured by DWI are useful for characterizing breast lesions on MRI. [5-8] Typically, malignant breast lesions demonstrate lower ADC values than benign breast tissue, reflecting higher cell density. [5]

Early work by Yamada et al. found statistically significant reductions in ADC values after gadolinium contrast agent administration in normal brain tissue (mean, -1.3%) and brain infarcts (mean, -3.5%). [9] In known breast carcinomas at 1.5T, Yuen et al reported dramatic ADC reductions (mean, -23%) after gadolinium administration. [10] A more recent study by Janka et al. also found a decrease in ADC after contrast in breast lesions [11], although the changes were smaller than reported by Yuen et al (mean, -11%).

The aim of the present study was to assess the Diffusion-weighted imaging effects of intravascular

contrast agent on apparent diffusion coefficient measures of ovarian neoplasms.

Materials and Methods

This was a Prospective Study was conducted on 50 patients at Department of Radiology, Katihar Medical College and Hospital, Katihar, Bihar, India with Study population being women with newly diagnosed ovarian tumors who underwent CEMRI study to evaluate the nature of tumor and extent.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Women referred from gynaec OPD for evaluation of ovarian neoplasms
2. With normal RFT

Exclusion Criteria

1. Failed to follow up in our institute with HPE reports.
2. Pregnant women were excluded from the study.

Protocol

MRI was performed with a Philips Achieve Tx 1.5 tesla (T) scanner using a dedicated abdomino-pelvic protocol. All pelvic MRIs included a T2-weighted fast spin echo sequence, T1-weighted non-fat-suppressed sequence, T1 weighted fat-suppressed DCE-MRI sequences, and DWI sequences before and after the DCE-MRI. Data collection performed according to the hospital regulations, after approval by the hospital authorities and consent by the patient.

Statistical Analysis

The data was entered in the Microsoft office excel 2007 and IBSS version 22 was used for analysis. The data was presented in the form of tables, and percentages. Paired t test was used to assess the statistical significance. P value of < 0.05 was considered significant.

Results

Table 1: Patient characteristics

Age Group of females (in yrs)	Numbers
20-40	6
40-60	20
>60	24
Ovarian Tumors	
Benign	30
Malignant	20
Size (in mm)	
<50	0
51-100	6
101-150	15
151-200	20
201-250	6
>250	3

Most of the patients belonged to >60 years of age. 30 were benign and 20 were malignant. Most of the patients had size of tumor from 101-200 mm.

Table 2: Benign tumors

Type of ovarian tumor	No of lesions	contrast ADC range	Pre contrast mean ADC	Post contrast ADC range	Post contrast ADC mean	P value
benign tumors	30	0.49,2.22	1.49±0.47	0.21,2.34	1.42±0.68	0.90
Serous cystadenoma	17	0.48, 2.21	1.54±0.18	0.52, 2.3	1.38±0.22	
Mucinous cyst adenoma	10	1.12, 1.79	1.48±0.20	1.22,1.88	1.52±0.18	
Fibro thecoma	1	1.2	1.2	1.22	1.22	
Cystadeno fibroma	1	0.89	0.89	0.9	0.9	
Brenner's Tumor	1	1.23	1.23	1.48	1.48	

In benign ovarian tumors, Pre contrast mean ADC was 1.49± 0.47 and Post contrast mean ADC value was 1.42±0.68 with statistically insignificant P value.

Table 3: Malignant tumors

Type of ovarian tumor	N	Precontrast ADC range	Pre contrast meanADC	Post contrast ADC range	Post contrast ADC mean	P value
Malignant Tumors	20	0.5,1.45	0.91±0.20	0.54,1.50	0.94±0.23	0.7
Serous Cystadeno carcinoma	10	0.66,1.35	0.97±0.20	0.70,1.37	0.99±0.22	
Mucinous Cystadeno carcinoma	5	0.65,1.31	0.89±0.19	0.68,1.35	0.92±0.23	
Serous borderline tumor	2	0.78,1.45	1.05±0.19	0.80,1.49	1.09±0.24	
Mucinous borderline tumor	1	0.99	0.99	1.31	1.31	
Clear cell adenocarcinoma	1	0.82	0.82	1.12	1.12	
Endometriod adenocarcinoma	1	0.93	0.93	1.23	1.23	

In malignant ovarian tumors, Pre contrast mean ADC was 0.91 ± 0.20 and post contrast mean ADC value was 0.94 ± 0.23 with statistically insignificant P value.

Discussion

Ovarian tumors are one of the main indications for gynecological surgery. Characterization of ovarian tumors preoperatively is important for explaining patients about possible management plan especially for the surgical part.

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is of great help in identifying malignant lesions, particularly when ultrasound findings are not optimal or indeterminate. MRI can reveal imaging features like papillary projections, nodularity, septae, solid component and signal intensity changes on T1- and T2-weighted images, but none of these criteria can accurately distinguish between benign and malignant nature of tumors.

Magnetic resonance (MR) diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI) use will help in better characterization of ovarian tumors. Diffusion-weighted imaging is dependent on micro diffusion of water alterations, in both intracellular as well as extracellular spaces. Differences in the apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC) of benign and malignant adnexal masses are reported to have proven value especially in complex lesions. Typically, malignant ovarian tumors demonstrate lower ADC values compared to the benign neoplasms, reflecting higher cellular density. The effect of gadolinium contrast agents on ADC measurements is not very well understood, and previous literature and studies have shown varied mixed results. [12,13]

Most of the patients belonged to >60 years of age. 30 were benign and 20 were malignant. Most of the patients had size of tumor from 101-200 mm. In benign ovarian tumors, Pre contrast mean ADC was 1.49 ± 0.47 and Post contrast mean ADC value was

1.42 ± 0.68 with statistically insignificant P value. In malignant ovarian tumors, Pre contrast mean ADC was 0.91 ± 0.20 and post contrast mean ADC value was 0.94 ± 0.23 with statistically insignificant P value. Several factors of our study design may explain why ovarian tumor ADC values were not significantly affected by contrast. These include field strength (3T versus 1.5T), contrast agent type, and repetition time (TR). [14,15] The late timing of the post-contrast DWI acquisition, approximately 9 minutes after injection, may also explain why our study did not identify significant alterations in lesion ADC. At this timing, much of the contrast has leaked from the microvasculature to the extracellular space (and perhaps even washed out of the tumor region). [16] Gadolinium is known to reduce signal-to-noise (SNR). As a result, the diffusion-weighted images may have a lower SNR, closer to the noise floor, and result in an artificially increased (or decreased, at higher b values) ADC calculation. [13]

Conclusion

ADC measures using our approach were not significantly changed after contrast administration for ovarian tumors at 1.5T. Our findings support the possibility that DWI optimized may be obtained before or after DCE-MRI without compromising important clinical information. Benign ovarian tumors had higher ADC values compared to malignant tumors, consistent with some of the previous studies.

References

1. Peters NH, Borel Rinkes IH, Zuithoff NP, Mali WP, Moons KG, Peeters PH. Meta-analysis of MR imaging in the diagnosis of breast lesions. *Radiology*. 2008 Jan;246(1):116-24.
2. Ei Khouli RH, Jacobs MA, Mezban SD, Huang P, Kamel IR, Macura KJ, Bluemke DA. Diffusion-weighted imaging improves the diagnostic accuracy of conventional 3.0-T

- breast MR imaging. *Radiology*. 2010 Jul;256(1):64-73.
3. Partridge SC, DeMartini WB, Kurland BF, Eby PR, White SW, Lehman CD. Quantitative diffusion-weighted imaging as an adjunct to conventional breast MRI for improved positive predictive value. *AJR Am J Roentgenol*. 2009 Dec;193(6):1716-22.
 4. Parsian S, Rahbar H, Allison KH, Demartini WB, Olson ML, Lehman CD, Partridge SC. Nonmalignant breast lesions: ADCs of benign and high-risk subtypes assessed as false-positive at dynamic enhanced MR imaging. *Radiology*. 2012 Dec;265(3):696-706.
 5. Guo Y, Cai YQ, Cai ZL, Gao YG, An NY, Ma L, Mahankali S, Gao JH. Differentiation of clinically benign and malignant breast lesions using diffusion-weighted imaging. *J Magn Reson Imaging*. 2002 Aug;16(2):172-8.
 6. Partridge SC, Demartini WB, Kurland BF, Eby PR, White SW, Lehman CD. Differential diagnosis of mammographically and clinically occult breast lesions on diffusion-weighted MRI. *J Magn Reson Imaging*. 2010 Mar;31(3):562-70.
 7. Rubesova E, Grell AS, De Maertelaer V, Metens T, Chao SL, Lemort M. Quantitative diffusion imaging in breast cancer: a clinical prospective study. *J Magn Reson Imaging*. 2006 Aug;24(2):319-24.
 8. Woodhams R, Matsunaga K, Iwabuchi K, Kan S, Hata H, Kuranami M, Watanabe M, Hayakawa K. Diffusion-weighted imaging of malignant breast tumors: the usefulness of apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC) value and ADC map for the detection of malignant breast tumors and evaluation of cancer extension. *J Comput Assist Tomogr*. 2005 Sep-Oct;29(5):644-9.
 9. Yamada K, Kubota H, Kizu O, Nakamura H, Ito H, Yuen S, Tanaka O, Kubota T, Makino M, Van Caueren M, Nishimura T. Effect of intravenous gadolinium-DTPA on diffusion-weighted images: evaluation of normal brain and infarcts. *Stroke*. 2002 Jul;33(7):1799-802.
 10. Yuen S, Yamada K, Goto M, Nishida K, Takahata A, Nishimura T. Microperfusion-induced elevation of ADC is suppressed after contrast in breast carcinoma. *J Magn Reson Imaging*. 2009 May;29(5):1080-4.
 11. Janka R, Hammon M, Geppert C, Nothhelfer A, Uder M, Wenkel E. Diffusion-weighted MR imaging of benign and malignant breast lesions before and after contrast enhancement. *Rofo*. 2014 Feb;186(2):130-5.
 12. Rubesova E, Grell AS, De Maertelaer V, Metens T, Chao SL, Lemort M. Quantitative diffusion imaging in breast cancer: a clinical prospective study. *Journal of Magnetic Resonance Imaging: An Official Journal of the International Society for Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2006 Aug;24(2):319-24.
 13. Chen G, Jespersen SN, Pedersen M, Pang Q, Horsman MR, Stødkilde-Jørgensen H. Intravenous administration of Gd-DTPA prior to DWI does not affect the apparent diffusion constant. *Magnetic resonance imaging*. 2005 Jun 1;23(5):685-9.
 14. Yuen S, Yamada K, Goto M, Nishida K, Takahata A, Nishimura T. Microperfusion-induced elevation of ADC is suppressed after contrast in breast carcinoma. *Journal of Magnetic Resonance Imaging: An Official Journal of the International Society for Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*. 2009 May;29(5):1080-4.
 15. Fırat AK, Şanlı B, Karakaş HM, Erdem G. The effect of intravenous gadolinium-DTPA on diffusion-weighted imaging. *Neuroradiology*. 2006 Jul;48:465-70.
 16. Chiu FY, Jao JC, Chen CY, Liu GC, Jaw TS, Chiou YY, Hsu FO, Hsu JS. Effect of intravenous gadolinium-DTPA on diffusion-weighted magnetic resonance images for evaluation of focal hepatic lesions. *Journal of computer assisted tomography*. 2005 Mar 1;29(2):176-80.